

Agroforestry "Farminar" as new mode of knowledge transfer

Introduction

Under certain conditions, contemporary agroforestry systems can be an economically and ecologically interesting way of optimizing land use for future (climate change-related) challenges, because they increase the productivity of an area without placing greater demands on natural resources. To raise interest, FiBL Austria (Research Institute of Organic Agriculture) has created an agroforestry farminar that ensures knowledge transfer on the topic for various groups, including practitioners and government agencies.

The farminar

In a farminar (a blend of the English "farm" and an "online seminar"), experts report directly from a farm, field or forest plot and present interesting work practices or equipment. People can participate on site as well online and ask questions via chat. Farminars thus stand for practical relevance and dynamism. Another plus point: they are recorded and posted online. The farminar format has been developed by an Austrian training institution for rural development. The agroforestry farminar, however, is the first of its kind.

The agroforestry farminar is based on the knowledge and experience that was collected in the OG and other projects. It was implemented at one of the OG farms. People attended the farminar in person and online. The overall question of the farminar is: What does agroforestry bring to the farm and the environment?

Lessons learned

What went well? Preparation and on-site technical implementation; hybrid format increased scope

What should be improved? More practical knowledge (less theory), alternative planning for bad weather event (there was a storm when the farminar event was held).

Figure 1: Agroforestry farminar in Austria (© Markut Theresia/FIBL)

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://agroforst-oesterreich.at/projekte/>

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